

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIAL SUPPORT AND STRESS COPING OF CLINICAL CLERKSHIPS WHO DO NOT LIVE WITH THEIR PARENTS IN SALEMBA, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This study aims to determine the relationship between parental social support and stress coping of clinical clerkships who do not live with their parents in Salemba, Jakarta. The samples in this study are 90 clinical clerkship who do not live with their parents. The hypothesis in this study uses a quantitative approach, using incidental sampling data collection technique to count the scores from social support scale questionnaire and a stress coping scale. Data analysis was performed using the bivariate correlation. The relationship between these two variables is shown by the correlation coefficient (r) = 0.460 and $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). The main hypothesis is that there is no relationship between social support of parents and stress coping of clinical clerkship who do not live with their parents. And the alternative hypothesis is that there is a significant relationship between parental social support and stress coping of clinical clerkships who do not live with parents. Based on these results, the main hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. From the results, the study concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between social support of parents and stress coping of clinical clerkship who do not live with their parents. This means that the higher social support from parents, the better clinical clerkships cope stress.

Keywords: parental social support, stress coping

1. Introduction

The growing number of medical departments in Indonesian universities took interest for the students to get in. Students who undergo medical education at higher education institutions must undergo a preclinical study period in the university before becoming a young doctor or clinical clerkship in the hospital. Clinical clerkships or often called as co-

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assistants in Indonesia medical students who have completed undergraduate programs and is trained medical profession programs. Clinical clerkship must take responsibility for everything they learned during his time as a preclinical student. After students go through preclinical study, students are immediately practice their ability to treat patients in the hospital. Such routine sometimes have dense and tense schedule, it would make the students more sensitive emotionally, feel bored, and overworked without a proper break. It is very possible for the students to experience stress.

There are many factors that determine how stress can be controlled and dealt with effectively, one of them is by stress coping strategies. Stress Coping is an effort to manage the situation and encourage individuals to solve life problems by finding ways to reduce stress (Lazarus in King, 2010; 51). Coping purpose is to balance individual emotions in stressful situations.

The success rate of using coping strategies varies between individuals, so to be able to solve problems and reduce stress, it is expected that there is help from other people. When a person experiences stress, they get social support from other individuals to the individuals concerned. Social support is information and feedback from others that shows that individuals are loved and cared for, valued, respected, involved in networks of communication, and mutual obligations (King, 2010; 226).

Having social ties is very important in coping, such as family or organization that can help when needed. In this case, parents are the first and foremost educators who have a big role in passing down good values to the students. No matter how small the social support provided by parents will greatly affect the individual concerned. Parents' social support also functioned to provide reinforcement for children in various ways. Especially, considering the many problems that must be passed by students while being clinical clerkships in the hospital.

This study aims to determine the relationship between parental social support and stress coping of Clinical Clerkship who do not live with their parents in Salemba.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Coping with Stress

According to Depanfillis (in Roberts & Greene, 2009: 104) social support is the best thought as a multidimensional construct consisting of functional and structural components. Social support refers to the actions that other people take when they deliver assistance. Social support can take place naturally in a variety of family, friends, neighbors, and peers, or within groups and organizations, specifically created or planned to achieve goals.

As stated by Ritter (in Nursalam M. N. & Ninuk D. K., 2007: 28) social support is one of the functions of social ties. Functional aspects include emotional support, encourage to express feelings, giving advice or information, and providing material assistance. Siegel (in Amie Ristiana, 2012: 12) argues that, social support as information

from others that shows that individuals are loved and cared for, have self-esteem, valued as a part of the communication network and shared obligations.

According to Canavan & Dolan (in Tarmidi & Ade, 2010: 217), social support can be applied to the family environment, such as parents. The social support given by parents to their children are either emotional, appreciation, instrumental, information or in groups.

2.2 Type of Social Support

House (in Nursalam M. N. & Ninuk D. K., 2007; 29) distinguishes 4 types of social support, namely:

- 1) Emotional Support. Includes expressions of empathy, care, and concern for the person.
- 2) Rewarding Support. It occurs through expressions of respect or positive appreciation for the other person, encouragement to go forward, agreement with the ideas or feelings of the person, and also positive comparisons of individuals with others.
- 3) Instrumental Support. Includes direct assistance. For example, parents, friends, or significant others lend money to the students who need or giving job for them.
- 4) Informative Support. Includes providing advice, advice, knowledge, and information and instructions.

2.3 Social Support Aspects

Hause (in Nur H. & Elina R. R., 2013: 48) classifies aspects in social support there are 4, namely;

- a) Economic aspects. Every individual needs support in the form of empathy, love, trust and the need to be heard by people around him and need others to discuss their future life plans.
- b) Rewarding aspect. Aspects of assessment can be in the form of reward and respect, as feedback to what the students did and can also take the form of positive social comparison or approval.
- c) Information aspects. The form of this aspect is indirect social support, for example providing the information needed or advice needed by the individual.
- d) Instrumental aspects. This aspect manifested in suggestions to facilitate individuals in positive-purpose behavior. It can be in the form of money, objects or work.

2.4 Stress

According to Maramis (in Sunaryo, 2004: 215) stress is any problem or demand for adjustment, therefore something that disturbs the balance of the individual. Stress can also be said to be the body's reaction or response to a psychosocial stressor, like mental stress or life burden (Dadang Hawari in Sunaryo, 2004; 215). Meanwhile, according to a

complete dictionary of psychology (Chaplin, 2005; 488) stress is a depressed state, both physically and psychologically.

In general, what is meant by stress is the body's reaction to situations that cause pressure, change, and emotional tension. As quoted by Grant Brecht (in Sunaryo, 2004 : 215), it is stated that stress is a disturbance in the body and mind caused by changes and demands of life, which are influenced both by the environment and individual appearance.

2.5 Stress Coping

According to Folkman, et al (in Taylor 2012; 167) stress coping defined as thoughts and behaviors used to manage internal and external demands that are considered as stressful situations. The process used by individuals to handle stressful demands is called coping, or the ability to overcome problems (Atkinson, et al., 2010: 378). Meanwhile, according to King (2010: 51) stress coping is an effort to manage the situation and encourage individuals to solve life problems and find ways to master or reduce stress.

Lazarus & Folkman (in Davison, Neale, & Kring, 2012; 275) said that, there are many similarities of how individuals responding stressful situations are coping concepts, like how individuals try to overcome problems or deal with negative emotions that elicited. The effects of stress can vary depending on how they face the situation.

Coping can be focused to problem solving or regulating various negative emotions caused by these problems. Finding comfort or social support from others is one example of coping that is focused on emotions.

2.6 Coping Strategy Forms

According to Lazarus, et al (in Papalia, Olds, & Fieldman, 2009; 402), coping strategy is divided into two forms:

A. Problem-focused coping

Involving the use of action-oriented strategies to eliminate, regulate, or improve stress-causing conditions. This type of coping usually used when someone sees a realistic opportunity to change the situation. This form of coping is divided into three aspects:

- 1) Cautiousness. Individuals think and consider several available problem solving alternatives, ask for the opinions of others, be careful in deciding things and evaluate strategies that have been done.
- 2) Instrumental action. Individual actions that are directed at solving problems directly, and arrange the steps that will be taken.
- 3) Negotiation. This aspect consist of a number of attempts by someone aimed at other people involved or is the cause of the problem to help solve the problem.

B. Emotion-focused coping

Sometimes called palliative coping, this coping strategy is intended to make better feels, to regulate emotional responses to situations that cause stress, to ease physical and psychological responses. This form of coping is divided into four aspects:

- 1) Escapism. Behaviors to avoid problems with how involving ones in a situation that is more agreeable and rewarding, for example eating, sleeping, it is biased also with smoking or sipping liquor.
- 2) Minimization. The act of avoiding problems by treating them as if the problem at hand is much lighter than it really is.
- 3) Self-blame. This is a passive strategy that is more directed into, rather than an effort to get out of the problem.
- 4) Seeking meaning. A process in which individuals look for the meaning of failure experienced for themselves and try to find aspects that he thinks are important in their life.

2.7 Stress Coping Type

Six types of stress coping according to Lazarus & Folkman (in Blonna, 2012: 47) are:

- 1) Health and energy. Healthy and strong individuals have more energy to overcome their problems than individuals who are weak, sick, tired, or weak.
- 2) Positive beliefs. Positive beliefs about themselves and the ability of individuals to control the lives of individuals throughout the life of her .
- 3) Problem solving skills. Problem solving is a source that can help individuals reduce stress.
- 4) Social skills. Life Skills effective social often being around people. The ability to have empathy and understand how other people feel when they experience stressful situations.
- 5) Social support. Social support generally refers to individuals who need emotional support, informational, or real.
- 6) Material source. Materials sources are goods and services that could be purchased with money may help overcome a potential stressor.

3. Methodology

Stress Coping is an effort made by individuals when faced with internal and external demands aimed at managing a stressful situation with the aim of reducing distress. Operated through scoring stress coping scale consisting of problem-focused coping and emotion-focused coping based on theories from Lazarus, Folkman, et al (in Papalia, Olds, & Fieldman, 2009; 402). Indicators of problem-focused coping are cautiousness, instrumental action, and negotiation. While emotion-focused coping indicators are escapism, minimization, self-blame, and seeking meaning. From the resulting score, it can be seen in the form of selected stress coping.

Parental social support is assistance or support received by individuals from parents in the form of verbal and non-verbal actions that influence the behavior and emotions in running life and the difficulties encountered. Social support is operationalized with scores obtained based on House theory (in Nursalam M. N. &

Ninuk D. K., 2007; 29) using the Social Support Scale which consists of emotional support, appreciation, instrumental support, and informative support.

The population in this study were clinical clerkships who did not live with their parents in Salemba. This sampling method is accidental sampling. Anyone who is met and included in the population category, can be a sample or respondent (Burhan Bungin, 2005: 126). With this method, the results of the distribution of sample scale obtained. The number of respondents is 90 people.

In this research the data collection method is using the Likert scale model, a measuring instrument that has special characteristics that can distinguish from various other forms of data collection tools such as questionnaires. It has five alternative answers that indicate a state of strongly agree (SS), agree (S), neutral (R), disagree (TS) and strongly disagree (STS).

Data analysis methods needed in this study are based on the objectives and research hypotheses. The null hypothesis tested is the main hypothesis, "There is a relationship between parental social support and stress coping." The statistical method used to test this hypothesis is bivariate correlation analysis to examine the relationship between predictor variable with the dependent variable. In processing the data analysis the researchers also used the SPSS program version 16.00 for Windows.

4. Result and Discussion

Based on the results of the normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk test, social support variable score were $p = 0,000 (<0,05)$ thus ordinal categorization scores assuming the data were not normally distributed. The results of the categorization calculation, found that social support is included in the high categorization with a mean finding of 119,12. Then the stress coping variable is scored $p = 0,000$, where $p < 0.05$, thus the categorization score is based on the ordinal category with the assumption that the data are not normally distributed. The results of the categorization calculation found that stress coping was included in the high category with mean findings 92,53.

This is supported by research conducted by Nur H., Elina R. R. (2013: 54) that there is a significant positive relationship between parental social support and coping with stress strategies. The results of this study indicate that parental social support factors play an important role in coping with stress on medical residency students who do not live with parents, that the higher the parent's social support, the higher the tendency for stress coping.

This is in line with the statement Lowenthal and Haven (in Evi Haryati, 2004: 29) social support from people who are personally close to the students, often giving advice and understanding them, has a very big influence in alleviating the stress that is being experienced. The support obtained will elevate good feelings; that the individual is loved, admired, respected, and all of which will create a sense of security and belongingness. This can reduce the stress felt by students in dealing with their problems.

5. Conclusion

Referring to the results of the analysis of the data, it concluded that there is a significant relationship with the positive direction between social support of parents and stress coping of clinical clerkship who do not live with their parents in Salemba. This means that the higher the social support obtained, the higher the stress coping strategy raised by students.

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